

ХУЛҚ-АТВОР ОМИЛЛАРИГА ТАЪСИР КЎРСАТИШНИНГ ВАЛЕОЛОГИК ЁНДАШУВЛАРИ

ШАРОФУТДИНОВА РУМИЯ ИНФАРОВНА¹

ТОЛИБОВА ЗЕВАР ХОЖИЕВНА²

¹⁻²БУХОРО ДАВЛАТ УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7435919>

Abstract: Every worker in production enterprises should know how to provide first aid to a doctor in the event of an accident. In this article, the author comments on first aid in case of injury.

Key words: Consequence of injury, accident, production sites, medical drugs, first aid.

It is known that the outcome of an injury largely depends on the help provided in time. Therefore, every worker should know how to provide first aid to a doctor directly at the scene of an accident. Specially trained to provide first aid in production enterprises, organizations, shops, departments, brigades, field sheds, farmers, workshops and other production sites. Sanitary posts are provided with pharmacies with the necessary medical drugs and dressings. Injuries in production are conditionally divided into organizational and technical types according to the causes of their occurrence. The causes of industrial injuries of an organizational nature include:

- 1) failure to follow instructions on safety techniques before performing daily work or work that is highly dangerous for the health of working people;
- 2) passing the instructions on safety equipment, but insufficient control of its observance during the execution of the work;
- 3) failure to use necessary protective equipment (goggles, mask, respirator, barrier, etc.) while performing work (various production tasks);
- 4) the presence of objects and things unnecessary for the work in the working area;
- 5) use of workers with insufficient skills in complex and responsible work;
- 6) absence of fences, fences and fences in places where there is a possibility of injury;
- 7) insufficient lighting of workplaces with a high risk to human health;

From the above, it can be concluded that the most effective means of preventing injuries in production are organizational measures. These activities include;

- 1) continuous monitoring and inspection of the enterprise's administration, technical safety specialist, and foremen and foremen to ensure compliance with the rules of technical safety, correct organization of work;
- 2) immediate release from work of workers who lose alertness under the influence of narcotics or alcohol, who violate the rules of technical safety;
- 3) stop working on broken or malfunctioning mechanisms and equipment;
- 4) regular medical examination of workers engaged in complex, attention-demanding work;
- 5) organization of permanent and periodic involvement of workers in technical training, including basic information on safety techniques;
- 6) to familiarize each employed worker with the rules of equipment safety, to give them sanitary and technical instructions;

7) not to allow the worker to work in additional work or in work other than his main specialty (profession). Prevention of industrial injuries due to technical reasons includes; First aid in case of injury and paralysis. The person providing the aid should wash his hands thoroughly with soap, if this is not possible, he should lubricate the fingers with iodine ointment. It is impossible to wash the injured area with water, clean it and touch it even with a torn hand. If the wound area is heavily contaminated, its surroundings can only be wiped with a sterile cotton swab or gauze. Non-bleeding, bruised, punctured, small injured areas should be lubricated with 5% iodine tincture and bandaged with an antimicrobial agent. If there is bleeding from the injured area, the first aid method will depend on the appearance of the bleeding. Bleeding is usually observed with bleeding of varying intensity when the integrity of blood vessels is broken. Bleeding external (when blood flows outside the body, over it) and internal (when blood flows in internal organs, tissues). Depending on the injuries of the blood vessels, there are several forms of bleeding. With an external arterial-pulse, the blood color is light-red, while it gushes from the wound, accompanied by general weakness in the body and severe pain in the injured part of the body. When a vein is injured, the blood begins to flow in black-red streaks. If the blood flows in the form of a single drop and the wound also bleeds, this is capillary bleeding. When an artery is injured, there is intermittent blood flow from the injury site.

Venous and capillary blood flow is stopped by plastering the injured area with material. To do this, a piece of gauze that kills germs is folded over the injured area, a layer of cotton wool is placed on it, and it is tightly tied with a bandage. Arterial bleeding is the most dangerous. In order to stop the bleeding in such an injury, it is necessary to tightly clamp the artery above the injury site, and if this does not stop the bleeding, use a tourniquet or a tourniquet. For this, a rubber tube, thread, belt, handkerchief, etc. are used. With a tourniquet, the injured area of the artery is tightly tied to the body at certain points from above. When the legs are injured, the most important way to stop the blood flow is to tie the leg tightly to the upper back. Before tying the harness, the legs are raised. Also, when the elbows are injured and bleeding from the artery is observed, depending on the appearance of the injury, they are tied with a bandage or substitute materials. At this time, it is necessary to bring the injured person to the nearest medical facility. If the wound is under the muscle or in such uncomfortable places, it is not possible to use a tourniquet. In this case, foam or other soft material is placed between the abdomen and the thigh. Then the legs are bent to the maximum and it is tightly attached to the upper part of the waist. First aid for broken and dislocated arms, legs, and other parts of the body should begin by immobilizing the broken parts and placing them in a comfortable position. In order to bind the broken places, it is convenient and pain-free. Boards and the like should be used in splinting the injured areas so that they cover both the lower and upper parts of the fracture. In the case of an open fracture, the bleeding should be stopped before dressing it. Providing first aid to a person injured in case of broken legs. In the event of a fracture of the spine, the injured person should be placed under a splint or a tennis stick. It is necessary to ensure that the injured person does not bend his body. If the injured person has a broken rib (there is pain when breathing), it is necessary to wrap the chest with a bandage or a towel when exhaling. When bones appear in the body, only medical care is allowed for them. In case of injury, the swollen areas of the lat are tightly bandaged and a cooling object is applied to the lat. Eating lat around the abdomen is very dangerous. In this case, the injured person should be taken to the hospital as soon as possible.

References:

1. Sharofudinova R.I., Asadullayev A.N., Tolibova Z.X. The Factors and Basic Concepts Determining Community Health. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. 05.Sep-Oct 2021 ISSN: 2660-4159) 376-379.
2. R.I Sharofutdinova, A.N. Asadullaev, Z.X. Tolibova. The Factors and Basic Concepts Determining Community Health. Central asian journal of medical and natural sciences 2 (5), 376-379.
3. Р.И Шарафутдинова, Г.С Муратова, М.Т. Турсунбаева. КОНЦЕПЦИИ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И ИХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ В СОЗНАНИИ СТУДЕНТОВ. Биология и интегративная медицина, 156-161
4. Муратова.Г.С, Шарофутдинова Р.И, Турсунбаева.М. Талабаларда экологик тафаккур ва тарбия тушунчаларини шакллантириш. Тиббиётда янги кун 1 (1(29)), 105-107
5. Муратова.Г.С, Шарофутдинова Р.И, Турсунбаева.М. Concepts of ecological thinking and education and their formation in the minds of students. Биология и интегративная медицина, 156-161
6. Р.И ШАРАФУТДИНОВА, Г.С МУРАТОВА, М.Т.К ТУРСУНБАЕВА. ПРИНЦИПЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ КОНЦЕПЦИИ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И ВОСПИТАНИЯ. Биология и интегративная медицина, 98-104
7. Р.И Шарафутдинова, Г.С Муратова, МТК Турсунбаева. Экологик таълим ва тарбия тушунчаларини шакллантириш тамойиллари. Биология и интегративная медицина
8. Р.И Шарафутдинова, Г.С Муратова, Г.А Жумаева, Ш.А Мустафаева Спорт тиббиёти фанидан амалий машгулотлар ўтказишда хамкорлик таълими усулларидан фойдаланиш-" Современное состояние, проблемы и перспективы медицинского образования.
9. S.R Infarovna, M.G Saitovna. Role formation of ecological thinking and education in higher education institutions. ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL 11 (2), 1400
10. Р.И.Шарофутдинова, Г.С.Муратова. Concepts of ecological thinking and education and their formation in the minds of students. Биология интегративная медицина электронный научный журнал, 156.
11. Р.И Шарафутдинова, Г.С Муратова, Г.А Жумаева, Ш.А Мустафаева. USING COLLABORATIVE LEARNING METHOD ON CONDUCTING PRACTICAL EXERCISES ON THE SUBJECT OF SPORTS MEDICINE. Новый день в медицине, 261-264
12. Р.И ШАРАФУТДИНОВА, Г.С МУРАТОВА, МТК ТУРСУНБАЕВА. ПРИНЦИПЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ КОНЦЕПЦИИ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И ВОСПИТАНИЯ. Биология и интегративная медицина, 98-104
13. R.I Sharofutdinova, A.N. Asadullaev, Z.X. Tolibova. The Factors and Basic Concepts Determining Community Health. Central asian journal of medical and natural sciences 2 (5), 376-379.

14. Z.H.

Tolibova, D.R. Qarshiyeva, N.R. Ochilova. The role of Human healthy and safe lifestyle in the period of global pandemic-covid 19. The American journal of applied scincer 2 (11)

15. D.R. Karshieva, F.A. Nazarova, Z.H. Tolibova. Atmospheric dust and its effects on human health ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal 11 (3), 1168.

16. Z.H. Tolibova, D.R. Qarshiyeva, N.R. Ochilova. The role of Human healthy and safe lifestyle in the period of global pandemic-covid 19. The American journal of applied scincer 2 (11)

17. G.S. Muratova, D.R. Qarshiyeva. Basic Symptoms of Infectious Diseases European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630) 13, 117-121.

18. Р.И.Шарофутдинова, Г.С.Муратова. Concepts of ecological thinking and education and their formation in the minds of students. Биология интегративная медицина электронный научный журнал, 156

19. Asadullayev A.N. The role of physical education and sports professionals in the organization of a healthy lifestyle in society. Journal of Innovations in Pedagogy and Psychology, 3rd special issue. Tashkent-2020. 31-36.

20. Asadullayev A.N., Ochilova N.R., Jabborova O.G. Healthy lifestyle (Healthy lifestyle) Academicia an international multidisciplinary research journal (ISSN:2249-7137, январь 2021, 1835-1841).

21. Sharofudinova R.I., Asadullayev A.N., Tolibova Z.X. The Factors and Basic Concepts Determining Community Health. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science (Volume: 02 Issue: 05 Sep-Oct 2021 ISSN: 2660-4159) 376-379.

22. Asadullayev A.N. Factors that ensure the necessary level of human health. Bulletin of Khorezm Mamun Academy Khiva-2021. 29-31.

23. Asadullayev A.N. The role of physical education and sports professionals in the organization of a healthy lifestyle in society. Journal of Innovations in Pedagogy and Psychology, 3rd special issue. Tashkent-2020. 31-36.

24. Asadullayev A.N., Ochilova N.R., Jabborova O.G. Healthy lifestyle (Healthy lifestyle) Academicia an international multidisciplinary research journal (ISSN:2249-7137, январь 2021, 1835-1841).

25. Баумуратов Р.С., Асадуллоев А.Н., Вахшудллоева М.В. Роль гигиены физического воспитания в правильном росте и развитии подрастающего поколения. «Молодой исследователь: вызовы и перспективы» Сборник статей по материалам ССXXVII международной научно-практической конференции № 32 (227) Сентябрь 2021 г. Москва, 158-164 с.

